

CURRENT STATE TEETH WHITENING PROBLEMS

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Annotation. A brief characterization of teeth whitening methods is presented. In recent years, methods of enamel brightening with hydrogen peroxide (carbamide) using activation by light sources have been actively developed. In the clinic of therapeutic dentistry are widely used lamps of "cold" light, which do not cause a significant increase in temperature. An example is the BEYOND Polus Advanced gas pedal system, which uses a combination of halogen light, LEDs and ultrasound. Light, LEDs and ultrasound. This device provides fast and effective teeth whitening with minimal risk of errors and complications.

Key words: teeth whitening, in-office enamel brightening.

Introduction. Pearly white teeth at this stage of society's development are considered an integral part of human beauty and health. A white-toothed smile is regarded as a sign of success. At the same time, sociological studies show that mental and physical attractiveness depends on both successes in personal life and achievements in industrial and social activities. Medicine, in particular dentistry, cannot ignore the human desire to be attractive, that is why teeth whitening is of great importance today, many patients are interested in the possibility to lighten their teeth.

Materials and Methods of Study. As long as only routine methods of enamel treatment were used in dentistry with acids or hydrogen peroxide, they were not widely accepted until the late 1980s, when the method of "dentist-prescribed, patient-performed overnight" dentist-prescribed, patient-performed overnight, lifetime safe whitening.

The needs of the population in aesthetic dentistry, including teeth whitening, have been increasing significantly in recent years. In parallel, the number of doctors recommending vital whitening and the number of patients with a positive effect of treatment are increasing.

Most dental professionals recognize the broad of the possibilities of utilizing methods of tooth brightening. Indeed, skilled interventions provide rapid effects while keeping teeth intact. New technologies and modern whitening systems offer patients the opportunity to have white teeth and a brilliant smile without the discomfort of extensive preparation of hard tissues and fabrication of prosthetic structures. This is why there is an increasing number of advocates for

conservative methods of removing stains from the tooth surface or correcting unsatisfactory enamel color.

The following main types of whitening systems can be distinguished, widely used in dental practice: for professional use in the clinic, for home use under medical supervision (with protection of the oral mucosa), whitening toothpastes.

Home whitening involves exposing your teeth to carbamide peroxide for several hours during the day or overnight under a special protective plate.

Whitening toothpastes whitening toothpastes are freely available and show their effectiveness mainly when used after professional whitening in a clinic or independent, doctor-supervised home treatment.

Intracoronary whitening of devitalized teeth is used as an important aesthetic procedure. Reducing the risk of uncontrolled tissue resorption is achieved by avoiding contact of concentrated solutions (30-35%) of hydrogen peroxide on the cementum of concentrated solutions (30-35%) of hydrogen peroxide on the root cementum. An alternative is sodium perborate sodium perborate mixed with water. It has a less pronounced effect of intra-dental whitening, but is characterized by a low damaging effect.

Professional methods include the application to the teeth concentrated hydrogen peroxide solutions activated by heat or light. For office whitening is also designed concentrated formulations of carbamide peroxide.

Analysis of the results of modern scientific research in the field of dentistry shows that at present it is possible to characterize as professional and effective those methods of teeth whitening, indications for the choice of which are justified and tested by clinical practice.

So-called home whitening prescribed by a doctor.

One variation of the method is known as "overnight safe bleaching". In these cases, carbamide peroxide formulations are used at a reduced concentration of (5 to 22%). The method is carried out at home by the patient with protection of the mucosa mucous membrane of the oral cavity with special device - a protective plate. Safe home whitening under the supervision of a dentist is indicated in cases of tooth discoloration in local and systemic lesions, acquired, congenital and hereditary anomalies, superficial and deep pigmentations.

Many patients, especially those with time constraints, prefer professional whitening. That's when you have to weigh "the pros and cons. For example, home treatment may require more than three visits to the dentist. In turn, in most cases, clinical (office) treatment involves two or even one visits.

Supervised whitening (under medical supervision) Involves the insertion a protective mouth guard (spoon, plate), filled with a whitening agent, including high concentration carbamide peroxide (35-40%), for 30 minutes (up to 2 hours). 30 minutes (up to 2 hours). The patient remains in the dentist's chair or waiting room until the mouth guard is the mouth guard is removed.

Clinical controlled whitening, like on-the-go treatment, when the product is placed in the tooth cavity under a hermetic dressing for 2-7 days, it is indicated for in the case of discoloration of decolorated teeth or the appearance of pigmented stains in the deep or superficial layers of enamel, dentin of a living tooth.

Enamel microabrasion involves the removal of superficial pigmentation or defects through chemical microdissolution and micro-abrasion of hard tissue by mechanical means. The method is indicated in case of slight roughness of individual areas or teeth against the background of superficial foci of enamel discoloration.

Professional (guided) whitening. It is performed by a dentist and is called "office" (clinical) treatment. This method is also known also known as active whitening, where high concentrations of hydrogen peroxide or carbamide are used against a background of high concentrations of activators, or gas pedals, such as heat, light or laser beams to enhance the whitening effect.

In-office whitening can be used in virtually all cases of tooth discoloration:

Superficial or deep pigmentation of both living and devitalized teeth. In-office whitening is effective in staining developed cracks or subsurface foci of demineralization. Of the systemic color disorders easier to correct lifetime pigmentation and age-related changes. The whitening process is faster compared to compared to the classical technique, if the gel is additionally activated after application to the teeth, e.g. by a light source (power bleaching), with a light source (power bleaching). Thus, photo whitening is 42% more effective than gel. without activation: teeth lightening by 8 to 10 shades on the chromatic on the VITA scale compared to the average 4-5 - at the chemical. However, when using light sources possible side effects should be taken into account. For example, mercury-halogen lamps in the process of operation emit heat that can cause dental hypersensitivity of teeth.

The use of laser is quite promising, especially in the elimination of deep tooth pigmentation. The method involves constant clinical supervision to ensure the safety of treatment, which is due to the high activity and sensitivity of the method.

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The most popular LED (Light-Emitting Diode) lamps - "cold" light sources that eliminate incandescent elements. Light-Emitting Diode (LED) lamps are "cool" light sources that eliminate incandescent elements. This reduces the risk of hypersensitivity to the teeth. Clinical observations have shown the minimal effect of LED sources on the local temperature increase of the tooth and surrounding tissues.

The Beyond cold-light lamp is becoming a common sight in the restorative dentistry clinic. The Beyond cold light lamp is gaining widespread use in the therapeutic dentistry clinic. In particular, the BEYOND Polus Advanced gas pedal is an improved version of the BEYOND Polus professional whitening system BEYOND Polus, which is designed for professional teeth whitening in the dental office. BEYOND Polus Advanced uses a combination of halogen lamp light, LEDs and ultrasound to provide radiation in a strictly defined wavelength range between 480 and 480 wavelengths. In a strictly defined wavelength range between 480-520 nm. This mode ensures the activation of BEYOND whitening gels and improves whitening results by up to 6-8 shades.

The BEYOND lamp generates the least amount of heat of any other system and offers a choice of 3 intensity modes.

The light flux can be directed to both teeth (optional Power Whitening) or to an additional polymerizer. Power Whitening) or to the optional polymerizer. Control The lamp is controlled via a touch screen display, a special remote control which the person holds in his/her hand during the treatment and can be alerted with an audible signal to a problem.

The modern design of the lamp is attractive to the patient, which increases interest in the tooth brightening procedure in general.

Contraindication for BEYOND whitening method Polus Advanced whitening is contraindicated if the patient has an allergic reaction or allergic reaction or chemical sensitivity to peroxides, resins or glycols. Pregnant or lactating women and patients under 16 years of age should not undergo the procedure.

This article presents a clinical case of professional enamel brightening of permanent teeth.

BEYOND transparent gel based on 35% hydrogen peroxide was used for whitening the crowns, the process of mixing the components of which is carried out in a mixer nozzle.

To lighten tetracycline for tetracycline teeth and deep pigmentation, a kit including sodium perborate and hydrogen peroxide was used, which are mixed before the procedure and applied to the teeth for 5-6 minutes, followed by standard whitening.

Activation of the reaction was carried out with a cold light lamp BEYOND in the mode corresponding to clinical picture.

- Low/Gentle - (low/gentle) - the light intensity emitted at this setting is 210,000 LX and is recommended for patients with high tooth sensitivity, fluorosis, hypoplasia or visible enamel defects (small cracks or chips). The treatment time with this setting the treatment time has to be increased, due to the low level of light emitted.

- Medium/Normal - The light intensity is 250,000 LX and is recommended for patients with healthy enamel yellow discoloration caused by staining foods, beverages and tobacco products. This regimen can also be used for moderate fluorosis, as well as in cases of moderate tetracycline-related staining.

- High/Intense - The light intensity emitted at this setting is 300,000 LX and is recommended for patients with tetracycline staining and gray age discolorations.

In order to maintain the results of office whitening, we offered to the patient an innovative system e-Bright home whitening system, in which the gel is activated by rows of LEDs embedded in the included mouthpiece to enhance the effect LEDs.

The ordinal numbering of the shades of the 16-color scale was used to evaluate treatment efficacy, which can be represented as follows.

It allows us to quantify the effectiveness of bleaching. For example, with color B3 (serial number on the color scale - 11) at the beginning of treatment after exposure the tooth has acquired the shade D2 (serial number - 4), whitening can be quantified as 7 ranks (points): 11 minus 4.

Using a digital camera. to record the color of the teeth before the procedure.

Conclusion. At the present stage of development of dentistry, teeth whitening is gaining popularity. Teeth whitening, which contributes to the improvement appearance, and therefore, to improve image of a person. In recent decades, there has been a rapid development of enamel whitening methods, including both simple manipulations (use of toothpastes) and complex technical devices and complex technical devices. Methods of activation (acceleration) of the removal of discoloration are becoming more and more widespread process of elimination of discoloration. An important requirement is to reduce the risk of

complications, including hyperesthesia. These conditions are met by the BEYOND cold BEYOND cold light lamp, which combines the light of a halogen lamp, LEDs and ultrasound. The result is an optimal whitening regimen with minimal risk of increasing sensitivity of the teeth and surrounding tissues.

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